

Capturing Industry Feedbacks on the Work Immersion Performance of Technical Vocational Livelihood Trainees: Basis for Curriculum Enhancement

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Abstract:- The immersion performance is studied to determine whether further intervention is necessary to help augment the current Senior High School (SHS) curriculum. Hence, this study aims to examine the performance of the technical vocational livelihood trainees. Seventy-one trainees were distributed to different partner companies and studied using a complete enumeration in the comparative survey design. The Department of Education's (Dep Ed) Guidelines for Work Immersion survey questionnaire was adopted.

The data were analyzed using the Scheffe test that compared the categorical data concerning the level of competency when grouped according to specialization. The independent t-test and One-way ANOVA have been utilized to get a significant difference between the male and the female trainees' performance. Findings revealed that trainees were very satisfactory in all competencies. The study showed that crop and animal trainees did not differ significantly but had significantly higher competency than the trainees in food technology except in attendance and punctuality. With the difference at the 1% level, female trainees perform better than male trainees in terms of attendance and punctuality, productivity/resilience, initiative/proactive, and attitude. The competencies in teamwork, communication, judgment/decision making, dependability/reliability, and professionalism were also found significant at a 5% level where female trainees have higher competency than male trainees.

This finding implies that male trainees need more attention, mentoring, and monitoring than their counterparts. It is recommended that the University's administrator view this feedbacking results to countercheck if the trainees' coordinator has dutifully followed the curriculum. These responsible people are expected to thoroughly develop trainees' life-long skills, work ethic, and values necessary to facilitate the transition to the workplace.

Keywords: *Competency bands, SHS Curriculum, Intervention, Learning skills.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Targeting a greater connection between education and the nation's development, SHS work immersion, a compulsory subject, has been incorporated into the curriculum. Thus, it becomes a mandatory requirement before graduation. The K to 12 Basic Education Program aims to develop the competencies, work ethic, and values relevant to pursuing further education or joining the world of work. This immersion allows learners to familiarize themselves with the workplace employment simulation and apply their competencies in actual work environments. This work immersion develops learners' life and career skills and prepares them to either postsecondary or be employed. As Dep Ed said, students undergoing immersion will earn while learning and have relevant exposure and experience in their chosen track.

With this, the Department of Education provides work immersion guidelines to ensure that learners will exit in their secondary years have already acquired skills and competencies (DepEd Order No. 30, S. 2017). These guidelines were based on the experiences of technical-vocational and modeling schools, industry partners, focal persons, and youth advocates. Moreover, to foster relationships and strengthen partnerships, these guidelines provide support to the department and the implementers and learners who will have access to suitable work immersion venues and other related resources. It is also expected that the partner institution will allow learners to enhance their communication, improve human relations, and develop good work habits that would prepare them for higher education or employment.

However, this work immersion poses a risk for assuring the quality of standards of practice if not adequately supervised and governed (Henderson & Trede, 2017). With this thought, feedback from the industry has to be conducted as part of the learning process. The feedback results of performance monitoring determine whether further intervention is necessary to help augment the curriculum (Gupta et al., 2014). This feedbacking enables and further develops trainees' skills and abilities to facilitate the transition to the workplace (Peach et al., 2014). Some existing programs are not producing graduates with lifelong learning skills to be successful. The Philippines Statistics Office declares that more than 60 percent of the 15 to 24

years old are in the labor force. By the education category, 28.9 percent of the unemployed are junior high school graduates, and 19.6 percent are college graduates. From 1994 to 2019, the unemployment rate in the Philippines averaged 8.31 percent (Employment Situation in April 2018, 2019).

A university student's quality is measured through the quality of the curriculum and its supportive academic environment and includes other contributory factors that are deemed necessary (Buenviaje et al., 2015). Often, providing feedback is seen as compliance rather than a genuine commitment to further learning and reflection; the full impact of the industry feedback should be framed and implemented to have the perspective of the trainees, the mentor, and the academic (Peach et al., 2014). Several available studies focus on immersion's medium and long-term impact on employability and employment. For example, Peach et al. (2014) studied the three possible approaches to industry feedback through the critical role of workplace supervisors, student and academic perspectives, and maximizing student agency. A recent study by Rowe (2017) investigated how immersion contributes to enhancing employability outcomes for students and graduates.

To effectively support the feedbacking strategies, the work experience is embedded in the curriculum; and to support the employability outcomes, the provision of quality assessment is in place. Given this, although the individual study has not been reviewed in-depth, they are of different issues and variations of immersion. There is a lack of studies investigating the industry feedback on the technical-vocational livelihood work performance and reviewing the SHS curriculum. This gap needs to be addressed since it entails redesigning a current curriculum. The practical implications of the result in the survey data can be used as baseline information to review the existing course program, develop a new plan, or for perceived benefits to future curriculum studies.

In summary, the present study determines the level of competency on the work immersion performance as feed backed by the industry in terms of teamwork, communication, attendance & punctuality, productivity/resilience, initiative/proactivity, judgment/decision making, dependability/reliability, attitude, and professionalism. Secondly, it evaluates a difference in the performance among the animal, crop, and food technology production trainees. Thirdly, it explores the difference between male and female performances. Though the impact of the trainees' immersion to the research stakeholders is equally essential, the variable is outside the scope of this study. The researchers of this study expect a broader reach of the outcomes to the various beneficiaries by sharing the findings.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used a comparative survey design utilizing a complete enumeration of 71 TVL trainees. Complete enumeration was preferred since the population was not huge where it could be less expensive, not time-consuming, and did not require many researchers to do the investigation. This method assesses individuals within a sampling unit. The dichotomous scale of 0 (male) and 1 (female) was applied to gather the gender information.

These trainees were in their Grade 12 in a university for the school year 2018-2019 and majoring in animal, crop, and food production- a technical-vocational livelihood track as an option to the other two tracks: Academic and Sports/Arts. As part of the work immersion guidelines, the student must pass the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) to obtain a National Certificate Level II (NC II). This NC I and NC II improve the employability of graduates in fields like Agriculture, Electronics, and Trade.

Upon weighing the significant value of the appraisal form to the research endeavors, the researchers downloaded the Work Immersion Appraisal Form Guidelines that serve as the survey feedback of the industries. The Department of Education issues the enclosed Guidelines for Work Immersion as a basis for implementing work immersion in all Senior High Schools.

With its senior high school principal and its technical-vocational livelihood advisers, the University identified industries where students could train. Visiting the industries was held, and when transactions were finalized, faculty meetings were facilitated. A Memorandum of Agreement between the University and the industries was made and signed.

Thus, before the work immersion ended, the team with its advisers provided the Work Immersion Appraisal Form to the industry employer and retrieved it days after. After recovering the appraisal form, a short conference between the trainee and the student's adviser happened; the trainee then signed the appraisal form to indicate that the trainee had prior knowledge of his rating. These collected data were then encoded, tabulated, and analyzed.

The Scheffe test compared the categorical data concerning the level of competency when grouped according to specialization. The independent t-test and one-way ANOVA have been utilized to significantly differ between the male and the female trainees' performance. The level of significance for statistical analysis is set at .01 and .05.

III. RESULTS

- What is the level of competency on the work immersion performance as feedbacked by the industry in terms of teamwork, communication, attendance & punctuality,

productivity/resilience, judgment/decision making, attitude, and professionalism?

initiative/proactivity, dependability/reliability,

Fig. 1: Percentage distribution of TVL teamwork competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Consistently works with others to accomplish goals and tasks.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
2. Treats all team members in a respectful, courteous manner.	3.98	Very Satisfactory
3. Actively participates in activities and assigned tasks required.	4.22	Outstanding
4. Willing to work with team members to improve team collaboration continuously.	4.01	Very Satisfactory
5. Considers the feedback and views of team members when completing an assigned task.	4.05	Very Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	4.08	Very Satisfactory

Table 1: Mean distribution of teamwork competency

Fig. 2: Percentage distribution of TVL communication competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Actively listens to the supervisor and co-workers.	4.16	Very Satisfactory
2. Comprehends written and oral information.	3.85	Very Satisfactory
3. Consistently delivers accurate information, both written and oral.	3.97	Very Satisfactory
4. Reliably provides feedback as required, both internally and externally.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	4.02	Very Satisfactory

Table 2. Mean distribution of communication competency

Fig. 3: Percentage distribution of TVL attendance/punctuality competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Is punctual regularly.	4.33	Outstanding
2. Maintains good attendance.	4.35	Outstanding
3. Informs the supervisor on time when absenteeism and tardiness may occur.	4.26	Outstanding
Over-all Mean	4.31	Outstanding

Table 3: Mean distribution of attendance/punctuality competency

Fig. 4: Percentage distribution of TVL productive/resilience competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Consistently produces quality results.	4.41	Outstanding
2. Meets deadlines and manages time well.	4.21	Outstanding
3. Can do multitasking.	4.09	Very Satisfactory
4. Can work under pressure and deliver the required tasks.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
5. Effective and efficient time management.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
6. Efficiently informs the supervisor of any challenge or hindrance related to a given task or assignment.	4.22	Outstanding
Over-all Mean	4.19	Very Satisfactory

Table 4: Mean distribution of productive/resilience competency

Fig. 5: Percentage distribution of TVL initiative/proactive competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Completes assignments with minimum supervision.	4.16	Very Satisfactory
2. Completes tasks independently and consistently.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
3. Seeks support as the need arises.	4.02	Very Satisfactory
4. Recognizes and takes immediate action to address problems and opportunities effectively.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
5. Engages in continuous learning	4.08	Very Satisfactory
6. Contributes new ideas and shares skills.	4.14	Very Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	4.10	Very Satisfactory

Mean

Table 5: Mean distribution of initiative/proactive competency

Fig. 6: Percentage distribution of TVL judgment/decision-making competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Analyzes problems effectively.	4.09	Very Satisfactory
2. Has the ability to make creative and practical solutions to problems.	4.18	Very Satisfactory
3. Demonstrates good judgment in handling everyday problems.	4.09	Very Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	4.12	Very Satisfactory

Table 6. Mean distribution of judgment/decision-making competency

Fig. 7: Percentage distribution of TVL dependability/reliability competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Can follow through and meet deadlines.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
2. Commits to his/her action.	4.14	Very Satisfactory
3. Can adjust quickly to changes in the workplace.	4.04	Very Satisfactory
4. Displays a high level of performance at all times.	4.07	Very Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	4.09	Very Satisfactory

Mean

Table 7: Mean distribution of dependability/reliability competency

Fig. 8: Percentage distribution of TVL attitude competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Offers assistance willingly.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
2. Shows a positive work attitude.	4.12	Very Satisfactory
3. Shows sensitivity to and consideration for others' feelings.	4.16	Very Satisfactory
4. Accepts criticism positively.	4.11	Very Satisfactory
5. Shows pride in work.	4.01	Very Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	4.10	Very Satisfactory

Table 8: Mean distribution of attitude competency

Fig. 9: Percentage distribution of TVL professionalism competency

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Respects persons in authority.	4.08	Very Satisfactory
2. Uses all tools, equipment, and facilities responsibly.	4.15	Very Satisfactory
3. Follows all policies and procedures when issues and conflict arise.	4.19	Very Satisfactory
4. Physical appearance conforms with the workplace and placement rules.	4.08	Very Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	4.12	Very Satisfactory

Table 9: Mean distribution of professionalism competency

- Is there a significant difference in the work immersion performance of animal production, crop production, and food production trainees?

Category	Mean	SD	F-Value	Significance
a. Teamwork				
Animal	4.31a	.46	25.511	.000**
Crop	4.49a	.47		
Food	3.30b	.85		
b. Communication				
Animal	4.27a	.42	22.287	.000**
Crop	4.45a	.55		
Food	3.21b	.98		
c. Attendance& Punctuality				
Animal	4.27ab	.43	12.815	.000**
Crop	4.65a	.40		
Food	3.87b	.77		
d. Productive/Resilience				
Animal	4.24a	.37	14.879	.000**
Crop	4.45a	.48		
Food	3.65b	.69		
e. Initiative/Proactive				
Animal	4.25a	.38	21.063	.000**
Crop	4.48a	.48		
Food	3.46b	.79		
f. Judgment/Decision Making				
Animal	4.18a	.34	17.395	.000**
Crop	4.51a	.48		
Food	3.53b	.85		
g. Dependability/Reliability				
Animal	4.23a	.39	19.509	.000**
Crop	4.45a	.46		
Food	3.46b	.81		
h. Attitude				
Animal	4.25a	.40	19.031	.000**
Crop	4.51a	.56		
Food	3.40b	.89		
i. Professionalism				
Animal	4.26a	.41	18.062	.000**
Crop	4.54a	.46		
Food	3.43b	1.01		

Table 10: Mean rating of industry feedback on work immersion performance of TVL when grouped according to specialization

** -significant at 5% level

- Is there a significant difference between the male and the female trainees' performance?

Category	Mean	SD	T-Value	Significance
a. Teamwork				
Female	4.23	.83	2.103	0.039*
Male	3.82	.68		
b. Communication				
Female	4.22	.87	2.450	0.017*
Male	3.71	.80		
c. Attendance & Punctuality				
Female	4.48	.62	2.983	0.004**
Male	4.04	.58		
d. Productive/Resilience				
Female	4.32	.64	3.122	0.003**
Male	3.87	.50		
e. Initiative/Proactive				
Female	4.28	.73	2.629	0.011**
Male	3.83	.61		
f. Judgment/Decision Making				
Female	4.28	.72	2.462	0.016*
Male	3.88	.66		
g. Dependability/Reliability				
Female	4.25	.73	2.396	0.019*
Male	3.84			
h. Attitude				
Female	4.30	.77	2.830	0.006**
Male	3.77	.75		
i. Professionalism				
Female	4.30	.86	2.299	0.025*
Male	3.85	.66		

Table 11: Industry feedback on work immersion competencies of TVL when grouped according to sex

*significant at 5% level

**significant at 1% level

IV. DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows that almost a quarter (23%) is rated with Satisfactory, which means the performance has met the required standard based on the given Work Immersion Guidelines. Trainees can perform duties with minimal supervision. The indicator that *treats all team members respectfully courteously gets the lowest Mean of 3.98*. This finding has aligned with the (*DepEd Order (DO) No. 30,s. 2017 Guidelines for Work Immersion, 2018*) that said to enrich students' skills in human relations and experience, the social interactions in a work environment are necessary skills that must be experienced during the exposure. An individual who cannot work on teams or achieve several tasks does not have the chance to be hired by successful companies; teamwork is a power that gives a group of

individuals a solid potential to make decisions (Sanyal & Hisam, 2018).

Results in Figure 2 disclose that almost half (48%) actively listens to supervisor and co-workers, comprehends written and oral information, consistently delivers accurate written and verbal communication, and reliably provides feedback as required, both internally and externally. Yet a noticeable ten percent (10%) of the trainees have been rated with Fair, which means trainees are less satisfactory and could be doing better in communication competency. One of the most important attributes needed in early career graduates identified by employers from all industries is oral and written communication (Grebennikov et al., 2014). This finding contradicts a study conducted by Morgan & Rucker (2013) wherein written communication got the highest-rated competency. The result shows a necessity to expose

trainees in both oral and written communicative situations, thereby exposing them to share ideas, opinions, thoughts, or concerns to deliver accurate information. This phenomenon is the Waterloo of the trainees. Communication conveys information and sophisticated and creative processes through which people interact at the workplace (Bergman et al., 2016).

As revealed in Figure 3, more than half (56%) are punctual regularly, maintain good attendance, and inform the supervisor when absenteeism and tardiness occur. A noteworthy eleven percent (11%) of the trainees are rated with Satisfactory only. This result means there is a need for minimal supervision in reporting to the industry. To improve students' punctuality issues, school discipline, such as formulating appropriate rules and regulations, is also necessary and systematic in practicing the rules on discipline matters (Sultana et al., 2013). Attendance-a building block must be in place to meet student achievement and goals (Bauer, 2018).

Figure 4 discloses that both Outstanding and Very Satisfactory ratings have forty-two percent (42%), respectively. This result provides an overall Mean of 4.19, a Very Satisfactory score. Trainees' performance fully met job requirements; they could perform what was expected. However, sixteen percent (16%) of the trainees were rated Satisfactory, which means there is a need for minimal supervision. The study's result is consistent with the study of Haynes (2007), who gave an example of the Hawthorne effect in which an individual alters their behavior because of the influence of the person making the changes, thus, motivating the workers to raise their productivity. The author concluded that the social factors were more important than the physical factors concerning productivity.

The data in Figure 5 reveal that less than half (42%) of the trainees can complete assignments with minimum supervision, complete tasks independently and consistently, seek support as the need arises. Recognize and take immediate action to address problems and opportunities effectively, engage in continuous learning, contribute new ideas, and share skills to improve the department/organization were additional tasks performed. Yet, almost a quarter (21%) of the trainees was rated Satisfactory, which means they need minimal supervision in this competency band. To solve problems on the job, develop action plans independently, and fulfill their work are the signs of employees with the initiative (Liu et al., 2015).

As found in Figure 6, less than half (44%) of the trainees had Outstanding judgment/decision-making competency. Twenty-one percent (21%) has been rated with Satisfactory, which means there is a need for minimal supervision. This finding affirms the Dep Ed Order that stated the work immersion would help develop life and career skills among the learners. Students should take control of their learning and even monitor it. Through this exposure, their judgment or decision-making will be put into practice as they need to decide whether to pursue postsecondary education or employment. To improve the

trainees' decision-making, provide intervention or training (Mendes et al., 2019).

This result in Figure 7 implies that less than half (45%) of the trainees can meet deadlines and adjust to changes. Still, one percent (1%) of the trainees show that their dependability/reliability partially meets the required standard, is less than satisfactory, and could improve. Watson (2004) stated that dependability could go with rewards and incentives that may be intrinsic or extrinsic.

The data in Figure 8 expose that almost half (48%) of the trainees had Outstanding attitude competency, but one percent (1%) of the trainees show that their attitude partially meets the required standard. It is less than Satisfactory and could be doing better. This finding corresponds to the study of (Hettiarachchi & Jayarathna, 2014) that showed a significant impact of work-related attitudes on the employees' job performance of the tertiary and vocational education sector in Sri Lanka. They further stated that this positive or negative attitude remains even if they change jobs or occupations. Employee attitudes affect behavior and are essential levers of organizational performance (Saari & Judge, 2004).

Figure 9 results reveal that almost half (48%) of the trainees had Outstanding professionalism competency. However, one percent (1%) of the trainees show that their professionalism partially meets the required standard. It is less than satisfactory and could be doing better. This finding is similar to the study of Salam et al. (2012). Their respondents stated that professionalism should be taught and learned through experience and reported that professionalism should be assessed formally. Over the traditional classroom model, immersing students within the context of an entire organization provides a considerable incremental improvement (Saltz et al., 2013).

A. Is there a significant difference in the work immersion performance of animal production, crop production, and food production trainees?

Table 10 discloses that crop production trainees have the highest competency rating among the three specializations in terms of all competencies. Although, based on the Scheffe test, the trainees majoring in crop and animal did not differ significantly in all competencies. Moreover, crop and animal trainees have significantly higher competency ratings than the trainees in food technology except in attendance and punctuality, where animal and food trainees' competencies did not differ considerably based on the Scheffe test. This result implies that animal and crop production who have already passed the Agricultural National Certificate Levels 1 and 11 (NC 1, & 11) before the immersion perform better than the food production and are advantageous. However, this claim needs further study and verification. This National Certificate Level 1 covers four common competencies: using tools, equipment, and paraphernalia, performing measurement and calculation, practicing Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) procedures, and interpreting technical drawings and plans. The National Certificate Level 11 includes the demonstration of the expected competencies and the

development of core competencies ("k to 12 Agri-Fishery Arts-Agri- Crops Production (NC I) Curriculum Guide," 2016).

The trainees' coordinator must see that the student must have undergone the required NC before the immersion. The curriculum guide is provided to guide schools in creating flexible work immersion arrangements for their learners, and providing options for work immersion is relevant to learners' purposes and needs. Peach et al. (2014) argued that for the feedback to be meaningful to students, it is vital to allow students to discuss the criteria to be used when it is to be given and how the input will be articulated. The defined perspective of the student, the industry mentor, and the academic must be explored (Peach et al., 2014). An education ignoring the complexities of work context is not reflecting actual practice (Saltz et al., 2013). The experience alone is not a guarantee of success through a growing body of evidence supporting a valuable strategy for promoting employability (Rowe, 2017; Palmer et al., 2018).

B. Is there a significant difference between the male and the female trainees' performance?

Table 11 presents the industry feedback on work immersion competencies of TVL trainees when grouped according to sex. The table shows that the female trainees perform better than male trainees in attendance and punctuality, productivity/resilience, initiative/proactive, and attitude. The difference was significant at the 1% level based on the independent t-test results. The competencies in teamwork, communication, judgment/decision making, dependability/reliability, and professionalism were also found significant at a 5% level where female trainees also have higher competency ratings than male trainees.

This finding is opposite to the study conducted by Smith (2011), where students between different genders showed significant differences. Males outperformed females in terms of the degree of leadership and innovativeness. A study by Malapit et al. (2019) confirmed that more women are disempowered than men. Disempowered women have more inadequacies than disempowered men. In fact, (Osabuohien et al., 2019) study revealed that male individuals are more favored in working. However, women are more engaged in the agricultural sector than their male counterparts. However, (Bandaranaike et al., 2015) study revealed no significant difference between male and female students in all cognitive and affective work skills, except communication skills where females applied communication skills better than males. Work readiness in the curriculum design should be at the center rather than mapping desirable graduate competencies to current learning activities (Rowe, 2017). Several personality researchers have continually shown that adult dispositional traits are durable after 30. Young adulthood is a time of considerable growth, learning, and transformation (Smith, 2011). Overall this finding indicates that there is still much room for improvement for the male trainees. These trainees still need to be honed in their competencies to perform better.

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